

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY

Mirzabekova Nargiza Rakhmatovna

MIA of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1 Tashkent academic

Lyceum English teacher

ABSTRACT

This research paper aims to identify the methodology of teaching English language at Primary School children and strategies to enhance the language skills. It is obvious that more than 50% of world population is bilingual. Thus, demand on language learning is growing up to day. The acceleration of globalization processes in the world, the transition to free market relations and the promotion of the introduction of high technologies in production increase the need for "linguistic capital", i.e. specialists who have a perfect command of foreign languages (especially English). In order to ensure quality and efficiency in foreign language education, the experience of reducing the age of learning/teaching foreign languages is becoming popular. This was caused by the widespread concept of "the younger the better / early is better". Hence, the authors try to scrutinize deeply the methodology of teaching English language and means of enhancement of language skills. It can be summed up that according to the research results, at present, that the results are unsatisfied. The authors find research gap in the field of language learning process. Below, some suggestions and language learning strategies are given for further investigations.

Keywords: teaching English; language learning; primary school; language skills; bilingual; methodology.

INTORUCTION

In this fast growing competitive world English has been spoken by one quarter of world's population. (1), English language has become a compulsory link language, "the lingua franca" (language that is adopted as a common language between speakers whose native languages are different) (2) in the world of language acquisition and in school education, it has been adopted as a subject, medium of instruction and examination as well. Most of the students learn English to enhance their competence and efficacy in education, training and work. Though their mother tongue and medium of instruction varies from one another their choice of second language in the school is undeniably English. Out of the world's approximately 7.5 billion inhabitants, 1.5 billion speak English that's 20% of the Earth's population. (2) However, most of those people aren't native English speakers. Such learner remains deficient to face the interview and participate in group discussions which make them feel inferior in the job market and work environment. The main obstruction for them to learn the language is the medium of instruction, students from medium of English could speak the English language comparatively better than the other medium of instruction, "once in a blue moon" some students pick up speaking English even from other medium, vise- verse English medium students fails to come up to acceptable standard to communicate fluently in English. In this case students of different backgrounds commit different types of errors in the learning process such as pronunciation, spelling, grammar and vocabulary usage. (3)

Mostly students pacify themselves for not speaking English fluently because of their medium of instruction, ambiance and background. This hitch will not highly impact them until they get

decline in the interviews and failure in competitive exams. The diplomatic ways to learn English language are as follows:

- Grammar-cum-Translation Method.
- The Direct Method.
- The Audio-Lingual Method.
- Communicative Language Teaching.
- Total Physical Response.

In language training Teachers play a vital role “A good learner can only be a good teacher” (5) that every teacher should bear in mind, and our teaching methods are changing every now and then according to the advancement of the technologies so teachers are also expected to be updated accordingly. In learning a new language process listening, reading louder and writing are the key factors to improve the vocabulary and mirror practice and practice is to gain confident for the learners, it's a challenge for the teachers to handle these types of students because they are late adolescents and matured so they cannot be treated so childish by giving them homework, imposition and punishment etc., but at the same time they have to be taught the basic things like rules of grammar and so on. This study intends on a comparative analysis of the students difficulties faced while learning English as a language from English medium students and other medium of instruction. The difficulties encountered by the students when they were taught in the similar manner. To carry out an analytical study, we underwent two stage of field work: (a) conducted analytical test and (b) personal interview for both the set of medium students and some teachers. The aim was to get a honest feedback and to analyze the data and bring out remedies and suggestions.

II .Motive of the study

In the language learning process different background students faces different types of problems in making mistakes while speaking a second language and the teacher's effort to analyze the error and to overcome the issues like grammar, vocabulary, fluency and pronunciation, also to conquer the fear of speaking a second language without errors.

1. Grammar-cum-Translation Method.

The name itself explains the functionality of the grammar-cum-translation method. This is one of the popular methods of teaching English in grammar orientation. However, it depends on a ton of interpretation. The technique is the conventional or 'old style' language learning method. A few nations approach this teaching style. The fundamental thought behind this strategy is that the students become familiar with all grammar rules to translate various sentences easily. Yet, many teachers recognise this technique as incapable since it does not include the spoken form of the language and communication skills are ignored. Furthermore, it does not allow the learners to think directly in the target language. Thus, it hinders the creation of a direct link between thoughts and expression. Consequently, this technique doesn't improve the student's communicative ability in the language but builds strong language writing skills.

2. The Direct Method.

The audio method is also known as the direct method, which involves thinking And speaking in English. Here the communication between the teacher and the student is strictly in English, and the student is barred from using their native language This way, the student can get a strong hold on the accent and fluency, the frequency of grammatical errors in this would

be less. This method is widely used as it helps the students learn the English language in a way a native English speaker would speak like and not the orthodox textbook way. The following principles and procedures that guide the natural method are,

Teachers and students both use the target language in the classroom.

Students tend to have daily sessions on vocabulary and sentences.

Grammar is instructed inductively.

3. The Audio-Lingual Method.

The audio-lingual method is also recognized as the Army Method. During the first world war, the American Armed forces started escalating oral courses known as the 'Military particular Training Program' (ASTP). Instructive organisations later received it as an audio-lingual method. It is among the common methods of teaching English and striking highlights of the audio-lingual method are,

Language teaching starts with communication; the material is educated before it is offered in composed structure.

The objective language is the study hall's main language; the student's primary language isn't utilised.

The teacher is the role model for the student; student-to-student interaction happens in chain drills.

The army method is identified with the natural method. The most significant difference between the audio-lingual method and the natural method is its focal point of teaching.

4. Communicative Language Teaching.

The thought behind this method is to help students convey all the more successfully and effectively in a sensible situation they may wind up in. So, this teaching includes focusing on essential capacities like thanking, complaining, suggesting, inviting, and requesting directions to give some examples. There are some learning and teaching techniques that can be used in Communicative Language Teaching class, for example, role play, information gap, language exchanges, simulation, discussion, games, pair work, and group work. All these techniques can engage the learners in the communication process. The Communicative Language Teaching approach focuses on giving students the skills to clearly and confidently communicate in real-world situations with native speakers of their target language.

5. Total Physical Response.

Total Physical Response, also called TPR, is a method that follows 'learning by doing'. For example, the new learner will learn English through a series of activities, "Close the door", "Stand up", "Open your book", and "Stroll to the window and open it." With TPR, the most significant aptitude is aural perception, and everything else will be regular. The majority of class time in TPR lessons is spent doing drills in which the instructor gives commands using the imperative mood. Students respond to these commands with physical actions. In the beginning, students learn the meaning of the commands they listen to by direct observation. After they learn the meaning of the words in these commands, the teacher provides a command that uses novel combinations of the words the students have learned.

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